

Stakeholder engagement activities - Initial

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DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc	
DMP	Data management plan	
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Glossary

Acronym/abbreviations	
ACS GCI	American Chemical Society Green Chemistry Institute
BPSA	Bio-Process Systems Alliance
BSI	British Standards Institution
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
C(D)MO	Contract (Development and) Manufacturing Organization
DG-ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
DG-JRC	Directorate-General Joint Research Centre
DMP	Data management plan
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEB	European Environmental Bureau
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EPLCA	European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment
EU	European Union
EuropaBio	European Association for Bioindustries
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
IHI JU	Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking
ISPE	International Society for Pharmaceutical Engineering
ISO	International Organization for Standardization

Acronym/abbreviations	
IQ Consortium	International Consortium for Innovation and Quality in Pharmaceutical Development
LCA	Life cycle assessment
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NIIMBL	National Institute for Innovation in Manufacturing Biopharmaceuticals
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEG	Pharmaceutical Environment Group
RTO	Research and Technology Organization
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SEA	Stakeholder Engagement Activities
TfS	Together for Sustainability
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the initial Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan, which is a strategic guide that outlines how PHARMECO will identify and engage relevant stakeholders throughout the project. The SEA Plan is essential to ensuring that the project remains inclusive, responsive, and aligned with both regulatory expectations and societal needs.

The plan's main goals include:

- Compiling and clustering a comprehensive list of stakeholder categories.
- Identifying priority stakeholders for early engagement.
- Developing outreach strategies to connect with key stakeholders and build lasting relationships.

Engagement will target a broad community, including industry, academia, regulatory bodies, healthcare professionals, patient groups, and civil society organizations. By stimulating open dialogue and collaboration, PHARMECO aims to accelerate the adoption of sustainable practices across the pharmaceutical value chain.

The SEA Plan is a living document and will evolve alongside the project. Regular updates will incorporate feedback from stakeholders and project partners to improve engagement approaches and ensure continued alignment with PHARMECO's objectives. Ultimately, this strategy supports effective communication, knowledge sharing, and long-term impact across the healthcare sustainability ecosystem.

1 Description of the deliverable's objective and the content

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan is a strategic document designed to guide the consortium's approach to identifying, engaging, and collaborating with relevant stakeholders throughout the project. Its objective is to ensure that stakeholder interaction is proactive, inclusive, and aligned with the project's overarching goals of advancing safe and sustainable pharmaceutical manufacturing.

From the early stages of the project, AbbVie, in collaboration with RISE, will coordinate stakeholders' engagement activities. These will include cross-consortium workshops, bilateral meetings, and other interactive formats, which may be organized by different PHARMECO working groups - extending beyond WP9 - depending on the topic at hand. A stakeholder list will be developed collaboratively with all consortium partners, drawing on their networks to identify relevant actors and cooperation opportunities. This will help stimulate early uptake of PHARMECO outcomes. Stakeholders' engagement in PHARMECO will cover strong interactions with Horizon Europe-funded initiatives (e.g., TransPharm, Eternal, Impactive, SusPharma etc), IHI/IMI projects (such as ENKORE and PREMIER), and influential initiatives (including PEG-LCA, NIIMBL, the American Chemical Society etc). These interactions aim to facilitate joint activities, promote synergies in tackling common challenges, and accelerate the uptake of PHARMECO's methodologies, tools, and best practices.

In addition, key external stakeholders, such as manufacturers not being members of PHARMECO, regulatory authorities (linked to Task 9.4), environmental NGOs, civil society actors (including patient groups, healthcare professionals, and consumer organizations), and European standards bodies, will be actively engaged. These interactions will help ensure PHARMECO's work remains responsive to emerging regulatory trends/policy developments and societal expectations, particularly within the evolving landscape of the EU pharmaceutical review.

2 Sections of the deliverables

2.1 SEA strategic goals:

The Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan aims to support PHARMECO's mission through the following strategic goals:

- **Comprehensive stakeholder mapping:** Identify and categorize stakeholder groups according to their relevance, level of influence, and alignment with PHARMECO's objectives.
- **Prioritization of key stakeholders:** Determine which stakeholders to engage first based on their potential impact on the project's core themes of sustainability and pharmaceutical innovation. A Mendelow matrix will be used as tool to help with prioritization.
- **Facilitation of dialogue and collaboration:** Establish effective channels for ongoing feedback, knowledge exchange, and collaborative activities across stakeholder groups.
- **Commitment to inclusive and transparent engagement:** Ensure that engagement efforts are equitable, open, and responsive, reflecting the diversity of stakeholder perspectives and evolving needs throughout the project.

2.2 Key Steps in the SEA Process

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan adopts a dynamic and structured approach to ensure meaningful and strategic engagement throughout the project lifecycle. The envisioned process includes the following key steps:

- **Stakeholder Identification and Categorization:** Stakeholders will be systematically identified and grouped based on their role, interest, and relevance to PHARMECO's objectives.
- **Prioritization:** Stakeholder groups will be prioritized according to the project's phase, the relevance to specific tasks, and their potential to influence or benefit from project outcomes.
- **Engagement Execution:** Engagement activities will be conducted through various channels, including the PHARMECO community platform, project events, bilateral meetings, and leveraging the networks of consortium partners.
- **Work Package Alignment:** Stakeholders will be mapped to relevant Work Packages and deliverables to ensure targeted and context-specific engagement.
- **Interaction Monitoring:** All stakeholder interactions will be tracked and contact information will be managed in compliance with GDPR, ensuring ethical and secure data handling practices.
- **Continuous Adaptation:** The SEA plan will remain a living document, regularly updated based on feedback from stakeholders and internal project developments to remain responsive and effective.

2.2.1 Stakeholder identification

The PHARMECO SEA plan includes a preliminary list of stakeholder categories, which serves as a foundational reference for engagement activities. This list (still growing) will guide efforts to reach out to the broader PHARMECO community and populate each category with relevant organisations and individuals.

Preliminary list of Stakeholders:

- Sector organizations (e.g., EFPIA, MedTechEurope, EuropaBio)
- Collaborative platforms and networks (e.g., ACS, ACS GCI Pharmaceutical Roundtable, Pharmaceutical Environment Group, Biophorum, NIIMBL, BPSA, IQ Consortium, PEG-LCA or “Pharma LCA”, Together for Sustainability (“TfS”), International Society for Pharmaceutical Engineering (ISPE))
- EU project consortia concerning more sustainable pharmaceutical practices (TransPharm, SusPharma, Eternal, Impactive, Enviromed, Enkore, Premier etc)
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) practitioners (e.g., EPLCA)
- Regulatory and policy-making bodies (e.g., ISO, UNEP, EMA, ECHA, EEA, European Commission, EU Parliament ENVI Committee, national ministries of health, and national drug regulatory agencies; Ministry of Health, policy makers)
- Policy and Scientific Advisory Bodies (PEF, DG-ENV, DG-JRC, HTA bodies/Networks)
- Standardization body (BSI)
- Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)
- Pharmaceutical and medtech manufacturers not being part of PHARMECO (IPSEN)
- Supply chain actors (e.g. Lonza)
- Suppliers of chemicals, consumables, and equipment (Sartorius, Cytiva)
- Environmental NGOs (e.g. European Environmental Bureau (EEB))
- Patient organisations (e.g. EUPATI)
- Public health-oriented platforms

This preliminary list of stakeholders will further grow and mature during the project. Stakeholder interactions and collaborations are being logged in an excel-based tool on the internal Sharepoint:

[External collaborations - overview.xlsx](#)

2.2.2 Stakeholder clustering and prioritization

The Mendelow Matrix is a strategic tool used in stakeholder analyses to help prioritizing stakeholders based on two key dimensions:

- **Power (or Influence)**
How much ability a stakeholder has to affect the project's success or decision-making processes. High-power stakeholders can influence funding, approvals, or strategic direction.
- **Interest**
How much the stakeholder cares about or is affected by the project. This could be based on how relevant the project is to their goals, values, or operations.

Stakeholders will be mapped into four quadrants, with engagement activities tailored according to their position. Priority will initially be given to those with high power and/or high interest. However, it is important to recognize that stakeholder priorities may shift over the course of the project.

Figure 1 Mendelow Matrix illustration

Figure 2 PHARMECO's preliminary stakeholders' list grouped into quadrants of Mendelow Matrix

The matrix divides stakeholders into four quadrants:

1. Key Players: High Power, High Interest (Manage Closely)

- **Regulatory and policy-making bodies** (e.g., ISO, UNEP, EMA, ECHA, EEA, European Commission, EU Parliament ENVI Committee, national ministries of health, and national drug regulatory agencies)
 - These organizations have significant power to shape regulations and policy and a strong interest in sustainable pharmaceutical practices.
- **Policy and Scientific Advisory Bodies** (PEF, DG-ENV, DG-JRC, HTA Networks)
 - These bodies are influential in shaping policy and have a vested interest in sustainability and pharmaceutical practices.
- **Sector organizations** (e.g., EFPIA, MedTechEurope, EuropaBio)
 - These organizations represent industries and have high power and interest in ensuring their sectors are compliant with sustainability standards and regulations.
- **Manufacturers**

2. Context Setters: High Power, Low Interest (Keep Satisfied)

- **Standardization body (BSI)**
 - Has power over standard-setting, but its interest may not be as focused on the day-to-day issues related to sustainability.
- **EU project consortia concerning more sustainable pharmaceutical practices** (e.g., TransPharm, SusPharma, Eternal, Impactive, Enviromed, Enkore, Premier etc.)
 - While they have influence due to funding and EU backing, their interest is focused on the specific goals of their projects rather than ongoing sustainability in the broader pharmaceutical sector.

3. Defenders: Low Power, High Interest (Keep Informed)

- **Collaborative platforms and networks** (e.g., ACS GCI Pharmaceutical Roundtable, Pharmaceutical Environment Group, Biophorum, NIIMBL, BPSA, IQ Consortium, PEG-LCA)
 - These groups are highly interested in sustainability and pharmaceutical practices but have less influence than regulatory bodies or sector organizations.
- **Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)**
 - They are highly interested in research and innovation in sustainability but do not have direct power over policy or industry-wide change.
- **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) practitioners** (e.g., EPLCA)
 - They have a keen interest in sustainability but hold limited power in terms of regulatory or industry influence.
- **Environmental NGOs** (e.g., EEB)
 - They have strong interest in sustainable practices but limited power compared to regulatory bodies or sector organizations.
- **Patient organisations** (e.g., EUPATI)
 - Interested in ensuring that pharmaceuticals are sustainable, but their power to influence policy or industry practices is relatively low.

4. Wider audience: Low Power, Low Interest (Monitor)

- **Suppliers of chemicals, consumables, and equipment**
 - Although involved in the supply chain, they may have low interest in the broader sustainability trends unless there is direct impact on their business model.
- **Supply chain actors**
 - These actors may have limited interest and influence in the sustainability discussions unless their operations are directly impacted.

2.2.3 Stakeholder engagement

The PHARMECO SEA plan is developing a structured workflow to guide stakeholder engagement efforts, which will be implemented once stakeholders have been identified and categorized. This workflow ensures that engagement is strategic, compliant, and aligned with the overall project goals.

Engagement Workflow:

- Prioritize stakeholders based on their level of power and/or interest to ensure focused and effective engagement.
- Map each stakeholder group to the most relevant PHARMECO Work Packages (WPs) to clarify roles and expected interactions. Some stakeholders may have wide interest in almost all work packages, whereas other may only engage with a single WP.
- Maintain a stakeholder activity log to track engagement history and evolving priorities. Currently, this is managed through an Excel-based document hosted on the internal SharePoint. An alternative may be a CRM database.
- Ensure GDPR compliance by identifying data protection requirements and implementing appropriate safeguards.
- Develop tailored engagement strategies for each stakeholder group, with attention to potential synergies across WPs and relevant external projects.
- Create a timeline for planned engagement activities, prioritizing outreach to high-impact stakeholders.
- Monitor and evaluate engagement efforts, ensuring that activities remain aligned with stakeholder importance and project needs.
- Define documentation protocols, specifying which outputs (e.g., meeting minutes, presentations) should be archived to support transparency and continuity.

Outreach activities to engage with stakeholders will include collaborative workshops, bi-lateral meetings, targeting scientific conferences. Where relevant, working groups will be installed and a series of workshops and webinars will be organized to engage with selected stakeholders.

2.3 Strategic alignment, Challenges and continuous improvement

2.3.1 Alignment with Project Goals

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan is designed to support PHARMECO's overarching mission of promoting the long-term adoption of innovative, sustainable pharmaceutical development and manufacturing practices. By fostering an informed and engaged

community across healthcare, regulatory, academic, and industry sectors, the SEA plan ensures that project outputs—such as research findings, case studies, and training materials—are effectively disseminated through various tailored channels.

2.3.2 Emerging Challenges and Proposed Solutions

1. Identifying actual stakeholders in the different categories

Challenge: Each category needs to be filled with actual organisations, people, contact details etc in order to engage with them.

Proposed solutions: Utilize the PHARMECO community to expand the list and collect suitable contact information for stakeholders.

2. Engaging with Key Stakeholders

Challenge: The stakeholder landscape in PHARMECO spans a broad spectrum of private, public, governmental, regulatory, and non-profit institutions.

Proposed Solutions: Conduct a systematic survey within the PHARMECO community to identify and leverage existing knowledge networks and pinpoint specific stakeholders for targeted engagement.

Involve stakeholders in PHARMECO communication by e.g. inviting them to comment, prefaces or round table discussions as part of webinars.

3. Choosing Appropriate Engagement Channels

Challenge: The diversity and geographic distribution of stakeholders necessitate a flexible, well-matched approach to communication.

Proposed Solution: Create a stakeholder-communication matrix to align engagement methods with specific groups. The community survey will also inform participation in key scientific meetings and related events. Stakeholders may be engaged via questionnaires.

4. Tailoring Messaging to Stakeholder Needs

Challenge: Effective engagement requires customized messaging for varied stakeholder profiles.

Proposed Solution: Collaborate with the communications team to produce targeted materials (e.g., handouts, slide decks, emails) suited to each stakeholder group.

2.3.3 Strategies for Future Improvement

The preliminary SEA Plan has been designed with adaptability as a core principle. Early feedback from internal reviews and stakeholder consultations will inform iterative updates to ensure relevance and responsiveness. The SEA plan will serve as a living document that evolves with stakeholder needs, project developments, and emerging challenges

3 Conclusion

This initial Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan provides an initial framework for PHARMECO stakeholders engagement activities throughout the course of the project. It outlines our approach to identifying, prioritizing, and engaging with individuals and organizations that have a role to play in advancing sustainable pharmaceutical practices.

Recognizing that stakeholder landscapes and project needs may evolve over time, this plan is designed to be adaptive. It will be continuously updated and refined based on ongoing feedback, internal learnings, and external developments to ensure it remains relevant and effective.

Ultimately, meaningful stakeholder engagement is essential to the success of PHARMECO. By fostering collaboration across industry, academia, policy bodies, healthcare professionals, and civil society, we aim to create a shared foundation for innovation and long-term impact. Through this inclusive approach, we will support the uptake of sustainable solutions and contribute to the broader transformation of the pharmaceutical sector.

4 Annex 1

Table 1: Overview of PHARMECO stakeholder groups approached so far (30/04/2024)

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
Key Players	High power, high interest	Regulatory and policy-making bodies	UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme is the UN agency that coordinates global efforts to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.	Invited to be part of scientific advisory board
			EMA ITF	Forum for early dialogue between innovators and regulators to support the development of new medicines and technologies.	
		Sector organizations	EFPIA MQEG/EHSEG	EFPIA's Manufacturing and Quality Expert Group – Environment, Health, and Safety Expert Group, which focuses on improving manufacturing quality and addressing environmental, health, and safety issues in the pharmaceutical industry.	Exploratory discussion on how EFPIA MQEG/EHSEG can support PHARMECO

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
Context setters	High power, low interest	EU consortia promoting more sustainable pharmaceutical practices	TransPharm	Horizon Europe projects focused on advancing greener pharmaceutical production, sustainable processes, and enhanced environmental safety throughout the entire medicine lifecycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mutual participation in workshops and assemblies to align on activities (avoiding duplication, synergies). Small overlap in consortium members promotes informal alignment
			SusPharma		
			Impactive		
			Eternal		
			Premier	IHI project aiming to improve the environmental sustainability of pharmaceuticals through better risk assessment, greener design, and innovative technologies.	Awareness and informal alignment via overlapping members
		ENKORE			
		Collaborative platforms and networks	ACS-GCI Pharmaceutical Round Table	American Chemical Society – Green Chemistry Institute Pharmaceutical Roundtable brings together industry leaders to promote sustainable practices and green chemistry in the pharmaceutical sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate In addition, the Director of Sustainable development group has accepted the role of PHARMECO scientific advisory member
			CAS	Chemical Abstract Service is a division of the American Chemical Society that provides comprehensive chemical information, including databases, research tools, and digital resources, to support scientific innovation and discovery.	Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate
			PEG-LCA = Pharma LCA		

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
				Pharma LCA consortium is part of the Pharmaceutical Environment Group and brings together industry leaders to improve the environmental sustainability of pharmaceutical companies	Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate
			BPSA	Bio-Process Systems Alliance industry association promotes the adoption and innovation of single-use technologies in biopharmaceutical manufacturing.	
			NIIMBLE	National Institute for Innovation in Manufacturing Biopharmaceuticals is a U.S. public-private partnership focused on advancing biopharmaceutical manufacturing innovation, education, and workforce development.	
			TfS	Together for Sustainability is a global industry initiative that promotes sustainable supply chains in the chemical industry through supplier audits, assessments, and collaboration on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards.	Invited to be part of scientific advisory board
Defenders	High Interest, Low Power	Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)	University of York, Professor Jason Snape		Invited to be part of scientific advisory board